

Foreign Direct Investment in China: Effects on Regional Export

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Abstract

This paper investigates the existence of a significant FDI-export linkage in China, using panel data at the provincial level over the 1995 to 2003 period. The theory of FDI proposes the possibility of an export creating effect. However, the empirical results show that if the model is correctly specified, there is no evidence for the existence of a significant FDI-export linkage. Because it is difficult to determine provincial exports, the emphasis is on the importance of including an instrumented lag of the dependent variable, to be able to produce a correctly specified model with unbiased estimates of the variables included. As a consequence, it may be concluded that the claims of the reference studies concerning the presence of a FDI-export linkage are not valid.

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1. Introduction

When looking at the flows of inward Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in the last twenty years, it can be seen that it brings about a diversity of new capital and technological know-how, thereby benefiting the recipients. Especially for less developed countries and emerging market countries these developments have been an important driver for their economic growth and transformation into a solid market economy (OECD, 2006).

FDI into the Chinese economy has followed a steady upward curve. In 2004 the figure was \$54.9 billion, the highest level in history. *There is little doubt that Hong Kong-based investors account for much of the direct investment into the mainland, but it would be too simplistic to ascribe the boom in Chinese FDI simply to “round-tripping” of investment and similar financial and statistical artefacts (OECD, 2005).*

Inflows of FDI reached to \$916 billion in 2005. The largest recipient of inward FDI was the United Kingdom, receiving an amount of FDI equal to \$108 billion; the United States was the second largest recipient. Among the developing economies the picture remains the same, with China (\$72 billion) and Hong Kong (\$36 billion) at the top, followed by Singapore, Mexico, and Brazil. Outflows of FDI amounted to \$779 billion, of which the developed countries remain the leading sources. In 2005, the Netherlands had the leading position with FDI outflows equal to \$119 billion, followed by France and the United Kingdom (UNCTAD, 2006).

The motivation for studying the case of China is straightforward. In 1978 China opened up its economy and therefore created expectations of potential new markets and investment opportunities for the rest of the world. Since the mid 1980s and in particular the beginning of the 1990s, this process has been accelerated, by significantly reforming the foreign investment regime. The liberalization in 1978, which applied only to four special economic zones, was further extended to broad areas. Also, restrictions on FDI were relaxed in important areas such as market access, domestic sale, and equity control. As a result, China received large flows of foreign capital which stimulated economic growth (Pingyao, 2002).

In November 2001, China was accepted as a new member of the WTO. The accession terms imposed by the WTO included reductions of tariff- and non-tariff barriers, and the relaxation of many ownership restrictions. Moreover, China's entry to the World Trade Organization (WTO) suggests that trade will play an important role in the country's future economic development. China has become one of the fastest growing economies in the world (OECD, 2001).

China's inflow of foreign capital equaled approximately \$64 billion in 2005, of which \$60 billion consists of foreign direct investment. About 70 per cent has been invested in the secondary sector, mainly manufacturing. In 1985, China received 3 per cent of world FDI, and 14 per cent of the total amount of FDI flowing into the developing countries; in 2005 these shares rose to 8.5 per cent and 23 per cent respectively (CSY, 2006). These developments are shown in Figure 1, plotting the FDI indicators for the period 1985-2005.

Figure 1.1
China's FDI Indicators

Sources: China Statistical Yearbook 2006 (CSY, 2006) and UNCTAD FDI online-database.

Looking at global competitiveness patterns, measured by shares in world exports, twenty economies account for over three quarters of the value in world trade. The list is

dominated by developed countries. However, when looking at the gains in world trade share during the period 1985-2000, mostly developed economies emerge, of which China has the leading position (UNCTAD, 2002).

China experienced a striking export growth which equaled \$27 billion in 1985 and \$761 billion in 2005; it was accompanied by a significant growth in FDI inflows, from \$2 billion in the first year to \$72 billion in the latter. The increase of the country's market share from less than 2 per cent to more than 7 per cent during this period indicates that the strong export growth was driven by an improvement of China's export competitiveness in all markets. The share of manufactured goods in China's total exports was equal to 49 per cent in 1985; however, in 2005 they made up 94 per cent of the value of China's exports (CSY, 2006).

So what role do MNEs play in China's trade performance? Foreign affiliates accounted for less than 2 per cent of total Chinese exports in 1985; however, in 2005 their share had risen to 58 per cent (CSY, 2006). In 2000, more than 90 per cent of exports by foreign affiliates were manufactured goods, in which machinery and equipment were the most important, and made up 44 percent of China's total manufacturing exports (UNCTAD, 2002). The development of China's and foreign funded enterprises' exports can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2
China's and FFEs' Exports

Sources: China Statistical Yearbook 1996, 2001, and 2006 (CSY, 1996, 2001, 2006).

A voluminous body of studies exists concerning the role of foreign direct investment in the Chinese economy. However, only a few studies have attempted to quantitatively isolate the effect of foreign direct investment on China's export performance. The first studies in the field provided insights regarding the trade impact of inward FDI on the national level in the United States (Lutz, 1987; Orr, 1991; Lipsey, 1991). Leichenko and Erickson (1997) carried on, by looking at how the economies of U.S. states and regions are influenced by international economic changes. Concerning the literature applied to China's case, the first work comes from Zhang and Song (2000), Sun (2001), and Zhang (2005). All these three studies built on the work of Leichenko and Erickson (1997), examining the effect of inward FDI on China's export performance at the provincial level. For the main purpose of this thesis, I therefore follow some of these studies.

There is no doubt that China's economic opening and its increase in international trade have benefited the country as a whole, however, the country's regional and provincial economies may have performed rather different in terms of economic growth, and specifically in export performance. Assuming the same regional or provincial settings, what are the determinants of regional export supply in China? And more specific, what is the effect of inward foreign direct investment on China's regional export

performance? These are some of the questions to be explored in this thesis, by using panel data at the provincial level over the 1995 to 2003 period.

The remainder of this thesis is arranged as follows. Section 2 gives an overview of the studies which are related to the research conducted here. Section 3 presents the theory of foreign direct investment undertaken by Multinational enterprises (MNEs) that makes the model valid for the aim of this research. In section 4 the model is worked out, building on the theory presented in this thesis and the concepts of basic open-economy macroeconomics. Section 5 gives the empirical specification and describes the explanatory variables, followed by some descriptive statistics of the dataset in section 6. In section 7 the results are presented and discussed. Section 8 concludes.

2. Literature Overview

There is a considerable amount of theoretical treatments of the FDI-export linkage, and since the end-1990s some relevant empirical analyses have been carried out. When looking at these studies it becomes clear that two different approaches are used, besides the common feature of applying cross-sectional panel data. On the one hand, analysis of the impact of FDI on export performance is conducted using a firm-level dataset. On the other hand, studies make use of provincial-level data. We will discuss them here respectively.

There has been a growing literature on the FDI-export link in China. For example, Wu and Cheng (1999) investigate the determinants of export performance of China's township-village enterprises, using cross-regional data of China's non-state rural industrial sector. They found that foreign direct investment has a positive effect on the export performance in their sample. An empirical investigation by Liu and Shu (2003) using cross-sectional data at the industry level shows that the export performance of different industries is significantly influenced by FDI. Excellent work has been done by Wu (2003), who uses the factor-input version of the Heckscher-Ohlin model and extends it by analyzing the impact of environmental factors, like foreign investment on trade, among Chinese regions. He finds that foreign direct investment has a positive impact on regional export performance. Van Dijk (2002) analyses export behavior of Indonesian companies, using a database covering all manufacturing firms active in 1995. He uses a variable reflecting foreign ownership and finds it to be significant and positive, indicating the positive effect of MNE association on export behavior. The study of Dueñas-Capara (2006) determines the firm-level characteristics affecting the export performance of firms in three main manufacturing sectors in the Philippines. The new econometric model tested for foreign affiliation and found that, among other factors, it has the most influence on a firm's export capacity.

For the purpose of this paper, a detailed overview of the studies focusing on the FDI-export linkage using cross-sectional panel data at the regional level will be given, as this thesis builds on these studies. There are three papers of interest in the context of this

thesis and they will be discussed in chronically order of time, irrespective of their importance.

Leichenko and Erickson (1997) consider the effects of FDI on the foreign trade of U.S. regions. Their study examines the relationship between manufacturing export performance and foreign direct investment in manufacturing industries across U.S. states for the period from 1980 through 1991. In their model, state export levels are determined by state levels of FDI and other explanatory variables. The model was estimated for manufacturing as a whole, and for five separate subsets of manufacturing industries. The regression model depicted in Table 1 was estimated for the whole sample using ordinary-least squares (OLS) with errors corrected for heteroskedasticity. The positive and significant parameters of the export- and FDI variables suggest that increases in exports and foreign-funded enterprises positively influence export performance in the following year. The level of new capital expenditures in the state is not a significant predictor of future manufacturing export levels, whereas exchange rates have a positive and significant effect. Overall, the model performs rather well, with an R-squared of 0.706.

Table 1
Determinants of exports

Explanatory variables	Parameter estimates	t value
Exports	0.769 *	17.80
FDI	0.147 *	7.10
Domestic Investment	0.083	1.60
Exchange rate	0.000 *	6.30
R ²	0.706	
N	526	

Source: Leichenko and Erickson, 1997.

Notes: Superscript * indicates significance level of 5%.

All are lagged log variables with the exception of the exchange rate.

Zhang and Song (2000) examine the relation between export performance and FDI across provinces of China for the period from 1986 to 1997. Export levels of provinces are modeled as a function of provincial levels of FDI and other explanatory variables.

The panel data used for their model covers three central municipalities and 24 provinces. Due to many missing data on FDI for Qinghai, Tibet, and Ningxia, they exclude these three provinces from their regression. It is necessary to comment on some of the econometric issues related to their model and estimation. Instead of using fixed effects estimation they chose to apply random effects, captured in the error term. Also, they estimated their model with generalized least squares estimator (GLS). Finally, to minimize causality between exports and FDI, they used current exports as the dependent variable and a lag of FDI as an explanatory variable. The linear form of their regression has been admitted to the first model in Table 2. The positive and significant parameters on Exports, FDI, and GDP growth suggest that they all influence export performance. The results on other variables, however, are unexpected. In Model 2, the estimated results under a pooled least-squares regression are qualitatively the same as those obtained by using the random-effect method. They also performed a regression excluding Exports from the model, and added a GDP variable to capture the impact of the overall economy on export performance, using the pooled-least squares method. Model 3 shows the results. All findings are consistent with the theory except the negative and significant result on exchange rates.

Table 2
Determinants of exports

Explanatory variables	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3	
	Parameter estimates	t value	Parameter estimates	t value	Parameter estimates	t value
Exports	0.946 ***	44.85	0.937 ***	39.94	-	-
FDI	0.033 ***	3.58	0.030 ***	2.82	0.293 ***	13.86
Domestic Investment	0.012	0.41	0.028	0.83	0.384 ***	2.75
MS	-0.001	-0.53	-0.001	-0.59	0.013 ***	3.06
Exchange rate	-0.042 ***	-5.01	-0.039 ***	-4.44	-0.179 ***	-8.72
GDP growth	0.001 ***	3.79	0.009	3.68	0.012 ***	3.09
GDP	-	-	-	-	0.455 ***	3.9
Constant	0.597 ***	4.69	0.660 ***	4.51	4.794 ***	17.09
R ²	0.972		0.973		0.826	
N	282		282		282	

Source: Zhang and Song, 2000.

Notes: *** indicates significance level of 1%. FDI, Exports, and Domestic Investment are lagged log variables. GDP is a log variable.

Sun (2001) conducts an empirical study of the impact of FDI on the export performance across the three macro-regions in China using provincial-level data. The data used in this study are panel data including three macro-regions (the coastal, the central and the west, a total of 29 provinces) over a 14 year period from 1984 through 1997. He made use of a panel model and carried out three regression analyses. The primary model tests the impact of FDI, domestic investment, and exchange rates on provincial exports in each region. He arrived at the second model by excluding Guangdong province from the coastal region-sub sample, excluding the year 1997 to test for possible influences of the East Asian crisis, and deleting the exchange rate variable to test for the strength of responses of exports to changes in FDI and domestic investment. The findings from this study confirm that the impact of FDI on exports varies across the three macro-regions of China. It is stronger in the coastal region than in the central region, although the parameters of FDI are positive and significant for both regions. In the western region the impact of FDI on exports is insignificant. The regression results of both models for the coastal area (12 provinces) during the period 1984-1996 are shown in Table 3.

Table 3
Determinants of exports

Explanatory variables	Model 1		Model 2	
	Parameter estimates	t value	Parameter estimates	t value
FDI	0.128 ***	5.41	0.146 ***	4.04
Domestic Investment	0.700 ***	10.68	0.893 ***	36.66
Exchange rate	0.171 ***	3.47	-	-
TIME	0.000	-0.98	0.041 **	-2.39
Constant	-0.363 *	-1.90	-0.992 ***	-21.17
N	144		144	

Source: Sun, 2001.

Notes: Superscripts ***, **, * indicate significance level of 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively. FDI is a lagged log variable. Domestic Investment is a log variable. Exchange rate is a lagged variable.

By drawing together the literature presented in this section, the research carried out in this thesis mainly builds on the work done by Zhang and Song (2000), and Sun (2001). In this thesis an attempt will be made to improve their model by using the most recent data available. The regression results of Zhang and Song (2001), and the selected results from the study done by Sun (2001), will be compared with the estimations from the study in this thesis. Primary attention goes to the specification of the models and the econometric estimation methods used. In this way, the results presented in this research can be evaluated. The main focus is on the export-FDI linkage within the model; therefore, the next section presents the conceptual framework behind this relationship.

3. Theoretical Background

3.1 Theory of FDI

The theories of FDI have been developed from two perspectives. The first is the international business perspective, and the theory described here builds on this work. The second perspective comes from mainstream economics, including trade-related models, strategic models, and internalization models. These models distinguish between two types of FDI, namely horizontal- and vertical FDI.

The analytical approach in this section is extracted from the work done by Navaretti and Venables (2001) and is constructed from the mainstream economic perspective. It rests on earlier theoretical contributions, of which the most important one is the OLI framework or ‘eclectic’ paradigm developed by Dunning (1977, 1981). In short, he states that firms choose to go multinational if 1) they have market power given by the ownership of firm-specific assets known as knowledge-capital, 2) they benefit from locating their plant abroad rather than at home, 3) they benefit from internalizing their activities rather than perform them through third party-market transactions. These three advantages make up the OLI paradigm constructed by Dunning to explain multinational activity.

Following the UNCTAD 2006 report, *the basic rationale for a firm in a (global) market economy is to increase or protect their profitability and/or capital value. One of the ways in which TNCs are achieving this goal is by engaging in FDI, either to better exploit their existing competitive advantages or to safeguard, increase or add to these advantages.*

Firms can realize production in a foreign country in two ways. The first is called ‘Greenfield investments’, through which a firm sets up a new physical plant. Another possibility to become active in a foreign market is through strategically horizontal and vertical mergers and acquisitions (M&As), which means that a firm buys existing assets or merges with a local firm in the foreign country (Schenk et al., 2002). These two ways of going multinational differ in important aspects, but they also have an important

similarity, as the activities in both cases become spatially more diffused (Navaretti and Venables, 2001).

One of the possible ways for a firm to split up its activities geographically is by duplicating parts of the production process, as a result the firm will control assets of a particular production process in the home country as well as in the foreign country. Investments with such a purpose are called ‘horizontal’ investments, because the same part of the production chain is duplicated and it is designed to serve local markets. Operating the same part of the production process independently means that certain economies of scale will be foregone; however, this is only true for economies of scale at the plant level, not at the firm level. Nevertheless, the extent of these plant-level economies of scale can be large.

The advantage of duplicating particular units or plants of the firm’s production process is that the trade costs associated with exporting the goods to the foreign market is for a significant part avoided. Local production will substitute the export of the final good and thereby the firm can save on transport costs and trade barriers. In other words, higher trade costs on the final good will encourage firms to become multinational through ‘horizontal’ investment. In the literature this is called the ‘tariff-jumping motive’ for FDI. Besides saving on trade costs there are additional advantages which result from being much closer to the foreign market, for example the improvement of the capacity to respond to local market conditions. Additionally, operating in a local market means that one is able to interact more accurately with its business environment, like local suppliers and competitors. In case of Export-platform FDI, local market access may be beneficial not only because of the local market itself, but also because of its proximity to other countries with high-income populations. For HFDI the most important trade-off is between the economies of scale foregone at the plant level, and the advantages of serving a local market through its own local production rather than through exports from the home country.

Another possible way for a firm to split off some of its activity is by function. In this case a firm will not duplicate some parts of its production process as with HFDI, but move one or more parts of the production chain to another country. The particular activities which depend on these moved parts will all be served through the new

establishment. Therefore, investments associated with this kind of geographical diffusion of the firm's activities are called 'vertical' investments, because the production chain is interrupted in its vertical dimension as some parts are relocated to a low-cost location. As a result, the firm may become less efficient in its activities. This is also referred to as loss of economies of integration, because it normally leads to an increase in trade costs for components shipped between the geographically diffused plants. These trade costs consist of import tariffs on components or final goods, packaging and freight costs, cost of time in transit which is especially substantial for goods with a short product life cycle and simply highly valued goods, and so on.

The most important reason for a firm to become multinational through 'vertical' investment is because of the input-cost differential. The costs of inputs can vary a lot among different locations and therefore firms tend to move specific parts of their production chain to countries where the inputs needed for this part of the production are relatively cheap. For example, a firm will shift a part of its production process which requires a lot of unskilled labor to a country where the wages for unskilled workers are relatively low. In the same line of reasoning, parts of the production process like R&D will be relocated there where skilled workers are abundant and therefore relatively cheap compared to other places. Obviously, investments like these are all encouraged by the possibility of saving on the firm's production costs. Yet, some aspects should be taken into account when considering the potential savings on production costs. First, factor costs like wages should be corrected for the quality of the factors. For example, if the wages of workers are relatively low but their productivity too, the net benefits do not have to be positive. Second, it was assumed that factor abundance is negatively related with its costs; however, this is only the case when the factor market is in equilibrium. Therefore, firms take notice of the costs of factors rather than the country-specific abundance measures. Third, a useful insight is the fact that upstream stages of a production process often have larger factor costs than downstream production stages. So one may expect the former to be relocated to countries where its specific production factor is relatively abundant. The last aspect which should be taken note of is that the extent to which a firm can benefit from saving on production costs through VFDI, depends on the differences in factor intensities used in the distinctive parts of the

production process. In case the factor intensities do not differ along the production chain, VFDI does not reduce the production costs and therefore a firm will not geographically diffuse its activities. For VFDI the most important trade-off is between the losses of efficiency and the benefits accruing from lower production costs when relocating specific parts of the production process to lower-cost locations.

3.2 Export Effects

Following Navaretti and Venables (2001), the effects foreign direct investment has on the host economy are transferred through different channels which can be organized into three groups; these are product market effects, factor market effects, and ‘spill-over effects’. Which effect will occur depends on the type of investment undertaken by the firm, as mentioned above, this can either be ‘horizontal’ or ‘vertical’ investment.

The first group of FDI effects can occur in the product market as a result of a multinational activity undertaken by a firm, leading to changes in the quantities the firm buys and sells in the home- and foreign market. Under HFDI, a firm will set up a foreign affiliate, thereby replacing the imports and saving on production costs. As a result, local firms that produce close substitutes may be forced out of their own market, and thus the product market changes. Moreover, if a firm enters the foreign market by M&A of an indigenous competitor, the number of firms in the market will decrease and therefore the market shares of the remaining firms will rise, which is an anti-competitive effect. But the opposite effect may occur as well when the firm entering the foreign market is more efficient. Some of the benefits may be even passed on the consumers as an increase in product variety and or quality, or even a price reduction.

The FDI effects classified as factor market effects may occur in both the capital market and the labor market. When MNEs enter a foreign market they will be in need of capital which they may raise from funds on the local capital market, however, most of the time there will be foreign capital inflow which changes the local supply of capital. The factor market effects in the labor market are often of a greater magnitude and thus generally get more attention; examples are the effect on the skill composition of the

demand for labor, the effect on the overall demand for labor, and the resulting factor prices.

Undertaking a FDI activity does not only change the performance of the MNE, but it may also affect the performance of local firms, and thus the host economy. The benefits that may arise for local firms are called 'spillovers', which are classified by Navaretti and Venables (2001) as technological or pecuniary externalities. Technological externalities occur when the effects of a FDI activity consist of costs or benefits that are not directly transmitted through markets. Pecuniary externalities appear when effects transmitted through markets are not fully paid for, so parties to the transaction may receive economic surplus.

Technological externalities are unintended knowledge spillovers between firms which include the transferring of technology, knowledge of market conditions, and the acquisition of labor skills belonging to firms who do not agree. One of the ways such an effect may occur is when an employer working for a MNE is acquired by a local firm, and brings important technological know-how or market information with him. For the local firm the FDI activity created benefits but for the MNE this is an unintended knowledge spillover. Another spillover which is more or less the same for both parties arises when a supplier of components acquires the firm-specific technology of the MNE.

A clear illustration of a pecuniary externality is the scenario where both the MNE and a local competitor of substitutes make use of the same supplier of intermediates. When the MNE demands a certain quality standard from the local supplier, the local competitor will benefit from this by using the same components. In this case the local firm receives benefits through market transactions but does not fully pay for it.

The scale of the transmission of spillovers depends on a variety of country- and industry-specific characteristics. Navaretti and Venables (2001) assert that the most important factor determining the scale of spillovers is the absorptive capacity of the local firms, in other words, their proximity to MNEs. This is especially important because spillovers only arise when local firms and MNEs intensively interact with each other. Also, MNEs can only be advantageous for local firms through spillovers if these local firms possess a certain minimum of technological skills in order to absorb and make use of modern technology brought by the MNE.

Another important factor affecting spillovers is the existence of vertical linkages between MNEs and local firms. In case a local firm functions as a supplier of a MNE, it can receive some benefits through spillovers as MNEs support these local suppliers in setting up production processes, provide them technical support, and by training their employees to enhance the quality of the product they supply.

For the aim of this thesis the effects of foreign direct investment on the export performance of a host country can be determined from the theory presented here. A distinction can be made between direct and indirect effects. The direct effect in the FDI-export linkage stems from VFDI and platform-export FDI. The direct effect of VFDI is straightforward as it usually is trade-creating (opposite to HFDI which substitutes for trade), because products at different stages of production are shipped over international borders. The other direct effect comes from export-platform FDI, which is described by Ekholm, Forslid, and Markusen (2003) as investment and production in a host country where the output is largely sold in third markets, instead of the parent or host-country markets. It is not found in the current FDI theory, which is built largely on two motives for firms to invest in other countries, namely to better serve a local market or to get lower-cost inputs. Export-platform FDI contains elements of both motives. Often, production is meant to serve a large integrated market like the EU or the ASEAN with a production plant like in horizontal investments. However, a specific location within the region is chosen to save on production costs like in vertical investments.

Following Baltagi, Egger, and Pfaffermayr (2005), third-country effects should be important since the average country pair is relatively small as compared to the rest of the world, even if we consider a large parent's outward FDI. They also state that under complex FDI, the strength of third-country effects depends on a host country's relative remoteness from third markets.

Indirect effects can occur through the product market as MNEs increase competition in the domestic market. This may force local firms to become more efficient, which makes them more competitive in the world market, and thereby increasing exports. The most indirect effects probably accrue from 'spillovers', which may be technological or pecuniary externalities.

Both the direct- and indirect effects based on the theory above, should explain the FDI-export linkage in the model presented in the next section.

4. The Model

The macroeconomic environment can be analyzed from three broad perspectives, namely the short run, medium run, and long run. In the short run the focus is on the determination of the demand for goods. The framework consists of the goods market, which looks at the equilibrium and the determination of output by focusing on the interaction between demand, production, and income. And the financial markets, which look at the equilibrium and the determination of the interest rate. Putting these markets together it becomes possible to think about how output and the interest rate are determined in the short run. This framework is called the IS-LM model and captures a large part of what happens in the economy in the short run. Besides the basic macroeconomic mechanisms in this framework, ‘openness’ plays an important role. ‘Openness’ has three distinct dimensions, namely openness in goods markets, openness in financial markets, and openness in factor markets. In this thesis primary attention goes to the openness in the goods market. Openness in this dimension means that consumers and firms have the opportunity to choose between domestic and foreign goods in the equilibrium (Blanchard, 2000). Following the IS-LM model described above, in an open economy where foreign trade is possible the demand for domestic goods is given by

$$Y = C + I + G + (M - X) \quad (1)$$

In equation (1) the terms between brackets, $(M - X)$, reflects the external/foreign sector. The last term, X , expresses the value of foreign demand for domestic goods. These are goods that are domestically produced but sold abroad, called exports. The sum is called net exports and makes up the current account on the balance of payments.

In relation to the interactions between the macro model and the external sector, and especially the exports of domestic goods, it can be assumed that exports depend on spending decisions made by foreign consumers or firms that purchase domestic goods and services. Therefore, in this model exports will not change as a result of changes in domestic national income and is treated as exogenous.

For the aim of this paper we take the ‘openness’ element out of its context (national output determination) and focus us from here on entirely on the export function. The demand for domestic goods by foreign residents will depend on two factors: the level of consumer’s income (that is foreign income) and the price competitiveness of domestic goods in foreign markets, the latter being a simple application of the law of demand.

With all other things held constant, the higher the level of foreign incomes the greater will be the demand for domestically produced goods. Thus there will be a positive relationship between domestic exports and foreign real income, Y^* . The second influence on the demand for domestic exports is their price competitiveness. If home goods are to be competitive in the foreign market then their prices must be compared with locally produced substitutes, this can be done by looking at the price ratio. The price ratio, EP^*/P , is referred to as the real exchange rate ϵ , or competitiveness. Where E is the nominal exchange rate, defined as the rate at which the currencies can be traded for each other (Blanchard, 2000). More precisely, the nominal exchange rate E is the domestic price of the foreign currency and P^*/P is the ratio of foreign prices to domestic output prices. A rise in ϵ means that domestic goods are relatively cheaper compared with locally produced goods. Similarly an increase in domestic output prices will make domestic goods more expensive in foreign markets and therefore, *ceteris paribus*, reduce the demand for domestic exports. Hence the real exchange rate affects domestic exports with a positive coefficient. If the domestic currency depreciates against other currencies, other currencies appreciate against the domestic currency. This makes domestic exports cheaper for foreigners and they will want to buy more of them. This is confirmed by Erjavec and Cota (2004a, 2004b), whose state of the art econometric time-series studies show that the real exchange rate (and production capacity) are important determinants of Croatian export supply.

Before exports can be written as function of foreign income and the bilateral real exchange rate, two assumptions about the model are made. First, it is assumed that only two trading areas exist; the domestic country and a foreign country (or group of countries). The second assumption is that no impediments to free trade such as tariffs and non-tariff barriers like quotas exist. In line with the reasoning described above, and the assumptions made, the export function can be written as

$$X = X(Y^*, \varepsilon) \quad (2)$$

where

$$X_{Y^*} = \partial X / \partial Y^* > 0 \text{ and } X_{\varepsilon} = \partial X / \partial \varepsilon > 0$$

Having the theoretical framework from section 3, a variable can be added that reflects the represented relationship between the inflows of foreign direct investment and domestic exports. In the study of Wu and Cheng (1999), it is found that foreign direct investment is an essential determinant of the export performance of TVEs. They argue that foreign direct investment stimulates exports because it brings market access, modern production technologies, product specifications, and management skills. However, FDI also helps to bypass China's restrictive control on foreign trade rights. The FDI-export linkage explained by the direct and indirect effects isolated in the previous section captures these factors as well, and will be represented in the model by including inward foreign direct investment.

Additionally, the relationship between export supply and production capacity (business cycle variable) will be subjected to the analysis. Therefore production capacity variables, measured by GDP, are integrated into the model (Erjavec and Cota, 2004a). This relationship can be explained by the macroeconomic concept of business cycles.

When referring to the business cycle, one talks about the shorter-term cycles in GDP, which generally have duration of approximately five to ten years from peak to peak. Most sectors or industries undergo an increase in output during a boom and a fall in output during a recession. Often these sectors are classified as those producing investment goods (capital), consumer goods, and services. The growth rate of investment goods normally fluctuates more than the growth rate of the other two sectors. The reason for this greater volatility of investment goods in the capital sector can be explained by the accelerator theory of investment (Lipsey and Chrystal, 1999).

One important aspect of cyclical fluctuations is the variation in investment. In the basic macroeconomic model, investment changes as a result of changes in the interest rate. Besides interest rates, the accelerator theory recognizes another important determinant of investment which effect is captured in a dynamic model, namely GDP.

The occurrence of a recognizable pattern in investment fluctuations arises because the level of investment is related to changes in GDP. Investment depends on changes in final demand, and therefore on changes in GDP. The theory assumes a quick and solid change of investment in response to changes in sales, and thus to changes in GDP. This is based on the assumption that changes in output as a result of changes in the desired capital stock follow a proportional relationship. In the literature this relationship is referred to as the capital-output ratio. The accelerator only partially explains variations in investment capital. However, this does not mean that it is not an important factor in explaining the cyclical variability of investment, and therefore it should be taken into account. Another important aspect on these kinds of business cycle theories is that they respond with a certain lag in time (Lipsev and Chrystal, 1999).

Now that the theoretical background of the extension is discussed, the export function is rewritten as

$$X = X(Y^*, \varepsilon, FDI, GDP) \quad (3)$$

where, in addition to the other two derivations

$$X_{FDI} = \partial X / \partial FDI > 0 \text{ and } X_{GDP} = \partial X / \partial GDP > 0$$

Now that the model is built to explain the determination of a country's exports, and specifically captured the FDI-export linkage, the next section will give an empirical specification and explanation of the explanatory variables. Thereafter, a description of the dataset is given, supported by some time-series tests on the national level.

5. Empirical Specification

The study conducted in this thesis examines the relationship between China's export performance and inward foreign direct investment on the provincial level covering 31 provinces over a 9-year period. On the base of the model described in the previous section, provincial exports in year t are modeled as a function of previous exports, foreign direct investment, other investment, gross domestic product, the trade-weighted exchange rate, and a trend variable in each province. To measure the elasticity of changes in exports with regard to percentage changes in the explanatory variables, a logarithmic form of the export function is constructed in a dynamic model. The addition of a constant term and a stochastic component yields the following econometric specification

$$\ln \text{EXPORTS}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln \text{EXPORTS}_{it-1} + \beta_2 \ln \text{FDI}_{it-1} + \beta_3 \ln \text{I}_{it-1} + \beta_4 \ln \text{GDP}_{it-1} + \beta_5 \ln \text{WXR}_{it-1} + \beta_6 \text{TIME} + c_i + u_{it}$$

where EXPORTS_{it} is the total value of exports of province i in year t , $i = 1, 2, \dots, 31$ and $t = 1993, \dots, 2005$. EXPORTS_{it-1} is exports of province i in year $t-1$. The variables FDI_{it-1} and DFI_{it-1} are the levels of foreign direct investment and domestic investment for each province i in year $t-1$. GDP_{it-1} is the gross domestic product of province i for year $t-1$. WXR_{it-1} is the trade-weighted effective real exchange rate of the Chinese currency in year $t-1$. TIME reflects the year. The c_i term captures the unobserved individual effect for province i , u_{it} is the error term for province i in year t . The parameters β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 , and β_5 are the short-run elasticity of exports with respect to former exports, FDI, other investment, gross domestic product, and the trade-weighted effective real exchange rate of the Chinese currency. The parameter β_6 measures the change of exports due to the passage of time.¹ For the purpose of this thesis, the parameter β_2 on FDI is of special interest, as it measures the percentage change of exports as a result of a one per cent change in inward foreign direct investment.

¹ Parameter β_6 should be interpreted as, $\% \Delta \text{Exports} = (100 * \beta_6) \Delta \text{TIME}$.

Following Leichenko and Erickson (1997), the effects of FDI on export performance are not likely to be felt immediately because diffusion of new production technology, modernization of production facilities, or other changes requires time to take effect. The same is true for other investment. As mentioned in the previous section, business-cycle theories rely on time-lagged responses. Expectations of the current year t , made in the previous year $t-1$, are based on the overall economic performance measured by GDP. Therefore, a lag-structure of gross domestic product is included to capture this response. Also the exchange rate is supposed to effect export performance with a lag, as many international transactions related to trade are set down in a contract which may not be modified in the very short run.

A lagged value of the dependent variable is included in the model to take into account for persistency of exports which may bias the estimations of the other right hand-sided variables. Zhang and Song (2000) state that there are significant relationships between past and future export performance and that this procedure is commonly used in regional economic analyses where there may be a strong tendency for past economic trends to influence future performance. The result of the persistency test performed on the exports variable described in the next section confirms this.

The other investment variable is included in the model because total investment in fixed assets is the main determinant of production capacity, which determines the domestic supply of commodities. Including the other investment variable in the model is thus intended to hold the effects of these other investments constant (Leichenko and Erickson, 1997).

Many economic time series have a common tendency of growing over time. In order to draw casual inference a time trend is included in the model to take into account unobserved, trending factors that affect both exports and the explanatory variables. Ignoring the fact that exports and FDI are trending in the same direction can lead us to falsely conclude that changes in one of these variables are actually caused by changes in the other variable. In that case, exports and FDI are correlated only because they are both positively trending over time for reasons related to other unobserved effects. In the next section it becomes clear that the variables presented in this section indeed show trending behavior.

6. Data and Descriptive Statistics

The data used in this study comes from a variety of sources. The model estimation is mainly based on provincial level data covering the period from 1993 to 2005. The primary source for the data used in this thesis is from *The National Bureau of Statistics of China (NBS)*, the most reliable data source available. It functions as an agency under the State Council, and is in charge of statistics and economic accounting in China. The *China Statistical Yearbook* is an annual statistics publication, which covers very comprehensive provincial data on yearly basis and some selected data series in historically important years. This study makes use of *China Statistical Yearbook 1996-2006* for the measures of exports, other investment, foreign direct investment, and gross domestic product at the national as well as the provincial level.

The economic data used to construct the trade-weighted effective real exchange rate of the Chinese currency (RMB) comes from two additional sources. The first being OANDA Corporation, who publishes bilateral historical currency averages on a yearly basis. The second is the International Monetary Fund (IMF), more specifically, the World Economic Outlook (WEO) database, which contains selected macroeconomic data series. For the construction of the trade-weighted effective *real* exchange rate, average yearly data on inflation was used in this thesis, measured by consumer prices with the index based on 2000=100. The descriptive statistics of the variables at the provincial level used in this study are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4
Descriptives

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Minimum	Maximum	Obs.
Exports	804,167	1,804,145	8,686	15,300,000	266
FDI	155,935	259,853	100	1,363,466	266
Other investment	3,550,000,000	2,760,000,000	1,199,934	9,830,000,000	266
GDP	3,270,000,000	2,490,000,000	1,184,456	9,970,000,000	266
Exchange rate	3.546	0.537	2.971	4.645	266
TIME	1999.026	2.586478	1995	2003	266

All variables are measured in USD 10.000, with exception of the exchange rate and trend variable. The exchange rate is the trade-weighted domestic price (Yuan) of the top ten export source countries' currencies.

The dependent variable Exports, is the total value of exports by location of China's foreign trade managing units. It refers to the actual value of exports carried out by corporations which have been registered by the local customhouse and are vested with the right to run export business. It is measured by units of 10.000 U.S. dollars.

Statistical data on investment in China by the *China Statistical Yearbook* is categorized as follows. Total investment in fixed assets is grouped by sources of funds. These include fund from state budget, domestic loans, foreign investment, self-raised funds, and others depending on the source of investment. Foreign investment refers to foreign funds received for the construction and purchase of investment in fixed assets (covering equipment, materials, and technology), including foreign borrowings, foreign direct investment, and other foreign investment. Of particular interest in this thesis is the definition of FDI, following the *China Statistical Yearbook*, it refers to the investments inside China by foreign enterprises and economic organizations or individuals for the establishment of ventures exclusively with foreign owned investment, joint ventures, and cooperative enterprises or cooperative exploration of resources, with enterprises or economic organizations in China. It also includes the re-investment of the foreign entrepreneurs. Notice however, that this study makes use of a variable consisting of FDI as well as foreign other investment to estimate the FDI-export linkage. The reason for this is that CSY in some years observed in this study does not make a distinction between the two. But as foreign other investment makes up such a small share of the FDI variable used, one may assume that it does not significantly influence the estimations. The FDI variable, FDI, is measured in units of USD 10.000.

Other investment, labeled as Other Investment, is calculated as total investment in fixed assets minus FDI and other foreign direct investment. As total investment is measured in 100 million Yuan, calculating domestic investment required to convert the Chinese renminbi into United States dollars applying the current bilateral exchange rate of these two countries. As a result, other investment is given in units of 10.000 U.S. dollars.

Gross domestic product refers to the final products at market prices produced by all resident units in a country or region. The variable for gross domestic product, GDP, is given in its value form which means that it reflects the sum of the value-added of all

resident units. It is measured in 100 million Yuan, therefore the amounts are converted into USD 10.000 units applying the same approach as used for constructing the other investment variable.

Determining the value of the Yuan becomes more complex when considering the overall China exports because most commodities are exported to multiple countries. In order to measure the value that accounts for how the Yuan is performing against the currencies of the most important export markets, an effective exchange rate is needed. This measure of value is constructed by taking the trade-weighted averages of the bilateral exchange rates and combining them into a single index. To construct the trade-weighted exchange rate of the Chinese currency, WXR, the ten largest source countries for China's exports were used.²

Before the empirical results will be discussed, the time-series behaviour of the dependent and independent variables on the national level will be examined, in order to get a better feeling of the data being analyzed. In the Figures 3.1-3.5, the behavior of dependent and independent variables over the time period 1985 through 2005 is plotted. As can be seen, all variables tend to grow over time. Therefore, some tests are performed on the two main variables reflecting the export-FDI linkage.

Figure 3.1
Exports 1985-2005

Figure 3.2
FDI 1985-2005

Figure 3.3
Other Investment 1985-2005

² See Appendix Table A.1 for a detailed derivation of the trade-weighted effective real exchange rate.

Figure 3.4
GDP 1985 -2005

Figure 3.5
Exchange rate 1985-2005

To measure the visual positive trends quantitatively, the variable in question is regressed on the year variable. The parameter estimate of the year variable can then be interpreted as the change in the dependent variable (i.e. exports) from one year to the next due to the passage of time. The results showed an upward trend for both exports and FDI.³ But, as trending time-series do not necessarily have to be highly persistent, an additional test was applied to both series.

An important aspect of time-series behavior is the presence of a unit root when considering an AR(1) process of the variable. As this study makes use of panel data, it will only be discussed briefly. A test for a unit root in the process of the exports- and FDI variable is carried out using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test, where a lagged change is included to clean up potential serial correlation. Both variables seem to follow a unit root process.⁴

Zhang and Song (2000) address the issue that FDI and exports could be simultaneously related, in the way that FDI determines exports in the one direction, while exports stimulates FDI in the other direction. They claim to minimize this problem by regressing exports on a lag of FDI. To be sure that this is indeed the case, a Granger causality Wald test is carried out on the two causality regressions, containing three lags

³ $EXPORTS_t = -287.217 + 0.152 \text{ TIME}$, t value = 36.96, significant at 1% level.

$FDI_t = -377.439 + 0.196 \text{ TIME}$, t value = 10.50, significant at 1% level.

⁴ $\Delta EXPORTS_t = 5.746 + 0.059 \text{ TIME} - 0.038 \text{ L.EXPORTS} + 0.283 \Delta \text{ L.EXPORTS}$, t_0 value = -1.31 > -3.60 $\rightarrow H_0: \theta = 0$ (unit root) not rejected. Where $\theta = \rho - 1$.

$\Delta FDI_t = 2.551 + 0.031 \text{ TIME} - 0.194 \text{ L.FDI} + 0.561 \Delta \text{ L.FDI}$, t_0 value = -1.65 > -3.60 $\rightarrow H_0: \theta = 0$ (unit root) not rejected. Where $\theta = \rho - 1$.

All are log variables except the time trend.

and the exogenous trend variable. The results confirm the statement that FDI Granger causes exports, and not the other way around.⁵

Now that the data and its time-series characteristics have been described, the following section present the results of the model used to identify the determinants of exports.

⁵ z Granger causes y if $E(y_t|I_{t-1}) \neq E(y_t|J_{t-1})$, as past z is useful in addition to past y. Where I_{t-1} contains past information on y and z, and J_{t-1} contains only information on past y. Here three lags.

For y = EXPORTS and z = FDI, $\text{Chi2} (3) = 8.92 > 7.81 \rightarrow H_0: \gamma_1 = \gamma_2 = \gamma_3 = 0$ rejected. FDI Granger causes exports.

For y = FDI and z = EXPORTS, $\text{Chi2} (3) = 0.36 > 7.81 \rightarrow H_0: \gamma_1 = \gamma_2 = \gamma_3 = 0$ not rejected. Exports does not Granger cause FDI.

All are log variables.

7. Empirical Results

In this section the econometric issues concerning the estimation of the model will be reviewed first. Then the parameter estimates of the regression will be discussed, and compared to the reference studies mentioned in the literature overview section.

The use of panel data in a regression analysis is a method of studying a particular subject within multiple sites, which is periodically observed during a defined time period. The advantage of using a dynamic panel data (DPD) model in this research is that it permits us to study the dynamics of China's provincial exports change with a short time series. By having both a time series and cross-sectional dimension, it is possible to improve the quality and quantity of data, which would be impossible in case of applying only one of these dimensions. In other words, the panel approach enables us a regression analysis with both a spatial and temporal dimension (Yaffee, 2003). In this study, the spatial dimension refers to the Chinese provinces, and the temporal dimension refers to annual observations of the dependent and independent variables.

Before the model resulted in the specification described in section 5, a judgment had to be made whether a static linear model with strict exogenous variables should be used, or a dynamic linear model with a lagged endogeneous variable. The appropriate estimation method depends on the assumptions on strict exogeneity and on the correlation between the individual effects and the explanatory variables.

In case a static linear model with strict exogenous variables would be applied to investigate the determinants of China's provincial exports, a so-called Hausman test was performed. From the test result it may be concluded that fixed effects estimation would be preferred, because the individual effects and the explanatory variables are correlated.⁶ Reason for this correlation may be exogenous province characteristics such as coastal access, location near a border, or differences in factor endowments that influence provincial exports. The fixed-effects estimator controls for these differences as it has constant slopes but intercepts that differ according to the specific provinces. In addition

⁶ Hausman test: $\text{Chi}^2(5) = 42.73 > 2.21 \rightarrow H_0: E(c_i|x_i) = 0$ (difference in coefficients not systematic) rejected. Fixed effects estimation preferred.

to the fixed effects estimation with robust Newey-West standard errors⁷, the model was estimated by taking the first differences with robust standard errors, in order to compare the results of both static models. In this way, it was checked whether or not the model is correctly specified. Because the two procedures yield dramatically different estimates for the parameters, and the exogeneity assumption holds as the explanatory variables are in lagged form (the time trend is always exogenous), it can be stated that the model is not correctly specified. In other words, some important determinants of exports are missing in the model.⁸

In order to be able to estimate the model in a correct way, a lagged dependent variable is included to solve the omitted variable bias problem. Furthermore, first differences are taken from the variables' observations to sweep out the individual effect and potential endogeneity of one or more explanatory variables (however, they are assumed to be exogenous). Besides, as the time-series behavior in the previous section showed strong persistency (having unit root), differencing the equation is straightforward. The resulting dynamic linear model is not strictly exogenous, because the lagged exports variable depends on the unobserved individual effect, regardless of being treated as a random or fixed effect. The exogeneity assumption implies that the error term and the explanatory variables are uncorrelated. To solve for the inconsistency, the lagged exports variable is instrumented by means of two instruments; its own second- and third lag. The model is then estimated by Generalized Method of Moments (GMM), based on the moment condition that the expected value of the instruments is uncorrelated with the error term.⁹

In the context of the final model specified in section 5, and its corresponding moment conditions, a variety of econometric tests were carried out to identify and solve potential problems that may have plagued the first differenced DPD model.

⁷ Breusch-Pagan test: $\hat{u}^2 = -2592.183 - 0.018 \text{ L.I} + 0.872 \text{ L.FDI} - 0.055 \text{ L.GDP} + 10.650 \text{ L.WXR} + 1.351 \text{ TIME}$, F value = 5980.27 > 2.21 $\rightarrow H_0: \delta_1 + \delta_2 + \delta_3 + \delta_4 + \delta_5 = 0$ (homoskedasticity) rejected. AR(1) serial correlation test: $\hat{u} = -1.621 + 1.142 \text{ L.}\hat{u}$, $t_{\hat{u}}$ value = 45.61 > 1.96 $\rightarrow H_0: \rho = 0$ (no first order autocorrelation) rejected. In addition, a test for second order serial correlation was performed, again, H_0 was rejected (F value = 5.41). Newey-West standard errors are robust against heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation.

All are log variables except the time trend.

⁸ See Appendix Table 2.

⁹ $E(u) = 0$, $E(Xu) = 0$, $E(z_t u) = 0$. The third condition is specific for 2SLS/GMM method. The GMM parameter estimates then follow from solving the corresponding sample moments.

First, the model was tested for homoskedasticity, which means that the error term has a constant variance conditional on the explanatory variables. If this is not the case, the estimators will still be unbiased and consistent, but the estimator of the variance of the error term is biased (not consistent). As a result, standard F- and t-tests are not valid. Therefore, a Breusch-Pagan test was carried out, which indicated the presence of heteroskedasticity.¹⁰

Another critical problem is serial correlation in the error term of the regression model. When the AR(1) process of the error term contains serial correlation, the lagged exports variable in the regression is not contemporaneous exogenous. This means that the estimators are not consistent and therefore useless. To test for serial correlation a first- and second order Breusch-Godfrey test is performed, as the results of this test are also valid when the model includes a lagged endogenous variable, here lagged exports. The results of the tests indicated that the error term suffers from second order serial correlation.¹¹

As both heteroskedasticity and second order autocorrelation are present in the final model, the parameters of the explanatory variables are estimated by means of the two-step efficient generalized method of moments (GMM) estimators, because it explicitly takes into account that the distribution of the differenced error term might differ across the Chinese provinces due to heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation (STATA help file).

The second- and third lag of exports are supposed to be suitable instruments for the first differenced lagged exports variable on the right hand side if it satisfies the criteria of instrument exogeneity and instrument relevance. Instrument exogeneity implies that the instrument and the error term of the DPD model are uncorrelated. The assumption of instrument relevance requires that the instrument predicts the lagged endogenous variable, in this study the lagged exports variable. Both criteria were tested by means of

¹⁰ Breusch-Pagan test: $\hat{u}^2 = -0.001 \text{ LD.FDI} + 0.00 \text{ LD.I} + 0.000 \text{ LD.GDP} - 0.038 \text{ LD.WXR} + 0.171 \text{ D.TIME} - 0.022 \text{ L2.EXPORTS} + 0.012 \text{ L2.EXPORTS}$, F value = 10.71 > 2.01 $\rightarrow \delta_1 + \delta_2 + \delta_3 + \delta_4 + \delta_5 + \delta_6 = 0$ (homoskedasticity) rejected.

¹¹ Breusch-Godfrey test: $\text{D.EXPORTS} = -0.224 \text{ LD.EXPORTS} - 0.069 \text{ LD.FDI} + 0.004 \text{ LD.I} + 0.011 \text{ LD.GDP} + 0.285 \text{ LD.WXR} + 0.101 \text{ TIME} - 0.202 \text{ L.}\hat{u}$, Chi (1) = 1.07 < 3.84 $\rightarrow H_0: \rho = 0$ (no first order autocorrelation) not rejected. In addition, a test for second order serial correlation was performed, H_0 was rejected (Chi2 (2) = 57.60). The first differenced lagged exports variable was instrumented by means of its own second- and third lag.

All are log variables except the time trend.

the Hansen J-test, and the first stage regression, respectively. The results indicated that the second- and third lags of exports are a suitable instrument.¹²

In Table 5, the estimate of the model specification is reported for three different samples during the period 1995-2003, by means of large sample statistics (z rather than t). According to Sun (2001), the effect of FDI on exports differs across three macro-regions in China. He makes a distinction between coastal, central, western provinces. The effect is stronger in the coastal region than in the central- and western region. Therefore, in addition to the full sample, two sub samples are created. In this thesis, the central and western regions are aggregated. This is illustrated in Figure A.1 and Table A.3. From the estimation results produced by Sun (2001), and the distributional indicators presented in the appendix, one may expect that the FDI-export linkage is stronger in the coastal region than in the inland region.

The sub samples were tested for the same potential problems as the full sample. As expected, both suffer from heteroskedasticity and second autocorrelation, however, the error term of the coastal subsample also contains first order autocorrelation. Again, the instruments proved to be relevant, but, the instrument exogeneity assumption for the coastal subsample does not hold (see Table 5). This should be taken into consideration.¹³ Yet, we can assume that the correlation is for the lagged exports variable and the error term is higher.

The starting point of this study is the regression on the full sample, applying the specified dynamic model. The parameter estimates presented in the first column are the elasticity coefficients of exports in response to a one per cent change in the explanatory variables (C.P.). The parameter of the FDI variable is unexpectedly negative and small,

¹² First stage regression: LD.EXPORTS = 0.008 LD.FDI - 0.004 LD.I - 0.002 LD.WXR - 0.141 L2.EXPORTS + 0.158 L3.EXPORTS, F value = 4.23 > 3.33 → H₀: $\pi_1 = \pi_2 = 0$ (instruments not relevant) rejected.

Hansen's J statistic: 1.14, Chi2 (1) p value = 0.285 → H₀: E(u z) = 0 (instrument exogeneity) not rejected. Excluded instruments are correctly excluded from the estimated regression. GMM in STATA reports Hansen's J statistic by default. The J statistic is consistent in the presence of heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation. The J statistics for the two sub samples can be found in Table 5. The combination of instruments applied in this study proved to be the most suitable; however, adding interaction terms is not considered and may improve the strength of the instruments.

¹³ Coastal subsample: F value BP test = 7.28, Chi2 value BG test first order = 2.10, and second order = 5.21, F value first stage regression = 5.21.

Inland subsample: F value BP test = 4.25, Chi2 value BG test first order = 16.45, and second order = 17.63, F value first stage regression = 5.39.

which means that FDI has no effect on exports during the period investigated. Moreover, the large-sample statistic belonging to the parameter β_2 is small, so the estimated elasticity coefficient is not significant. Looking at the statistical results of the lagged exports variable, the picture is very different. Holding all other factors constant, the positive and significant parameter β_1 suggests that the previous level of exports has a high effect on the volume of exports in the current year. Its value implies that a one per cent change in exports of the previous year brings about an increase equal to 0.4 per cent in exports in the next year. This finding suits with the strong persistency of exports shown in the previous section. Another interesting detail putted forward by the model regards to the trade-weighted effective real exchange rate. Its parameter estimate is relatively large and significant, with β_5 equal to 0.214, and a corresponding z value of 3.65. This means that a one per cent increase in the domestic price of the foreign currency basket, increases exports with 0.2 per cent. This finding confirms the theory of the role exchange rates play in an open economy discussed in section 4. Also, the year variable proves to be significant in the exports model, as it has a parameter of 0.065 and a z value equal to 5.97. This positive relationship between the passage in time and the value of exports was already identified by plotting the export variable over time, and the regression on a time trend. The parameter estimate for GDP is small but significant; however, a larger effect would be expected concerning the theory behind it. Other Investment is very small and not significant.

Table 5
Determinants of exports

Explanatory variables	Full Sample		Coastal sample		Inland sample	
	Parameter estimates	z value	Parameter estimates	z value	Parameter estimates	z value
Exports	0.41 *	1.66	0.296 **	2.07	0.933 ***	2.83
FDI	-0.043	-1.06	-0.029	-0.58	-0.021	-0.35
Other Investment	0.006	1.64	0.001	0.43	0.016	1.46
GDP	0.012 **	2.40	0.005	0.18	0.012 ***	2.04
Exchange rate	0.214 ***	5.97	0.178 ***	5.66	0.164 ***	3.00
TIME	0.065 ***	3.65	0.098 ***	5.65	0.025	1.10
F value	8.34		4.17		9.68	
J statistic	1.141		4.702		1.451	
N	233		96		137	

Notes: Regressions are estimated using GMM estimation on data for 1995-2003. The dependent variable represents provincial exports in China. All are first differenced, lagged log variables (with exception of the differenced time trend). Superscripts ***, **, * indicate significance levels of 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively. The full estimation results are available from the author upon request. The constant term is dropped because the first differenced TIME variable is perfect collinear with the constant term. Exchange rate = Trade-weighted effective real exchange rate.

Turning now to the third and fifth column in Table 5, the parameter estimates produced by the regression for the sub samples can be checked. Taking into account the uneven distribution of exports and FDI among the Chinese regions, it is expected that the effect of FDI on exports is larger for the coastal sample than for the full sample, and thus also for the inland sample. However, the estimation results look very different. The parameter of the FDI variable for the coastal sample is negative and very insignificant; the same is true for the inland sample. These results strike with the theory discussed earlier in this study, as one may expect that higher inflows of foreign direct investment lead to higher volumes of exports. But, as the parameters' z values corresponding to the three regressions are all too small to assume the parameters to be consistent, it reasonable to conclude that the FDI-export linkage is not sufficiently isolated. With respect to the strong persistency in the export series, the parameter estimates for the coastal- and inland sample are 0.296 and 0.933 respectively. The parameter on GDP is for the inland sample positive and significant, while being very small and insignificant for the coastal sample. The time trend is positive and significant for the coastal sample but not for the inland sample. The effect of Other Investment is negligible and insignificant for both samples. The J statistic for the coastal sample is large, indicating that the exogeneity assumption

for the instruments does not hold at a low significance level. As a result, the estimates might be inconsistent, and should be treated with care.

Again, the estimated parameters of the exchange rate variable are positive and significant. The effect of the exchange rate on exports for all three samples is not as large as expected from the theory. An explanation for this could be China's implementation of export processing zones in the coastal region and central regions mentioned in the introduction of this paper.

Export processing zones (EPZs) account for a large share of non-primary manufactured exports, where efficiency-seeking FDI generally plays a prominent role. It involves international trade (internal or external to MNEs), with significant flows of intermediate and finished goods sourced in different locations (UNCTAD, 2002).

Straightforwardly, an increase in the exchange rate makes the inputs necessary for the export-oriented activities more expensive, which leads to higher production costs and thus lower export supply. The share exports through processing trade increased from 12 percent in 1985 to 55 percent in 2005 (CSY, 2006). Therefore, the magnitude of the effect of the exchange rate explained in section 4 may be mitigated.

The results of this study are obviously different from the results discussed in the literature overview. As mentioned before, this study builds in particular on the work done by Zhang and Song (2000) and Sun (2001), therefore a comparison is made.

When the final results from this thesis are compared with the ones from Zhang and Song (2000), the following comments can be made. First, the parameter estimates for the effect of FDI on exports is in all three models significant. This is in contrast to the concerning estimations presented in this section. Yet, the size of the parameters in model 1 and model 2 are very small, and therefore not economically interpretable. On the other hand, the third model produces a large parameter estimate which is highly significant. Regarding the exchange rate variable, their estimated parameters are negative and not significant in the first two models. In the third model, a significant and positive-but very small-effect is found. This is probably due to the weak measure of the exchange rate effect, which is measured by the bilateral exchange between the Chinese Yuan and the U.S. dollar. While on the first sight the results with respect to the FDI-export linkage may look like quite of an achievement, some econometric issues should be addressed here.

Most importantly, Zhang and Song (2000) estimate the first model with Random effects estimation (GLS), therefore violating the strict exogeneity assumption described in this section. As a result, the estimation method yields inconsistent estimates, despite the fact that the bias disappears when the sample size goes to infinity. A more appropriate estimation method would be to instrument the lagged exports variable and applying 2SLS or GMM. In their second and third model they estimate the regression by means of Pooled least-squares. However, as the second model contains a lagged dependent variable, the unobserved effect is correlated with the error term because no instruments are used. As a result, the estimates are not consistent and thus biased for the second model. Noteworthy, the parameter of the FDI variable in model 3 is relatively large; this is the result of excluding the lagged exports variable. However, he adds a GDP variable which explains part of the lagged exports effect. Presenting a model with both variables would give some useful insights with respect to the specification of the model. This has been illustrated in Appendix Table 4. The analysis of the time-series behavior in section 6 showed that the variables follow an upward trend in the period 1985-2005, because no time trend is included, the explanatory variables may be overestimated.

By comparing the results of the coastal sample in Table 5 with the results from the coastal study (12 provinces) during the period 1984-1996 undertaken by Sun (2001), some interesting issues arise. In both model 1 and 2, he finds a relative strong and significant effect of FDI on exports. With regard to the inclusion of the domestic investment variable in the model-which is intended to separate the general investment effect from that of FDI-a strong effect is found. These results are in contrast with the parameter estimates in this thesis, as they were negligible and insignificant. Conversely, the estimated parameters for the exchange rate are more or less similar to the ones in this thesis. Also here, some comments should be made regarding the econometric methods used and the specification of the model. Sun (2001) applies GLS estimation to his static panel model, which is correct if one assumes that the unobserved effect is uncorrelated with the error term. On the other hand, the model specification has not proved to be correct. By not including a lagged exports variable, one can not conclude that all factors affecting exports are taken into consideration, despite the fact that these factors are captured by the lagged exports variable and therefore not specifically identified. As a

result, the parameter of FDI and the other explanatory variables may be biased. This is shown in Table A.4.

The regression results from this study presented here do not provide evidence for the FDI-exports linkage introduced in the theoretical section. Excluding the lagged exports variable from the model did not significantly change the parameter of FDI. This would suggest that the parameter of FDI is correctly estimated.¹⁴ Therefore, other factors should explain the MNEs' share of China's exports, reflected in the parameter of the lagged exports variable. In the introduction of this thesis it was shown that MNEs were responsible for a substantial amount of China's total exports. Following the theoretical part of this thesis, some important determinants affecting exports in a provincial export function, are indicators of sector-specific economies of scale, sector-specific trade costs, factor cost differentials as a result of endowment differences, tax differentials and policies, and the level of technology. It should be noted that these factors are difficult to include in a model, especially when regarding the availability of reliable data.

¹⁴ See Appendix Table 5.

8. Conclusion

In the introduction the importance of multinational activity in today's integrated world has been discussed, in particular the case of China. It was shown that MNEs are responsible for 60 per cent of the total exports in China. Therefore, in this thesis the effect of foreign direct investment on the China's exports has been investigated using provincial level data during the period 1995-2003. The theory of FDI proposes the possibility of an export creating effect. However, this seems not to hold in the case of China. By building on earlier work done in this field and improving the estimation of the effect FDI has on exports, section 7 presented the empirical results. It showed that if the model is correctly specified, there is no evidence for the existence of a significant FDI-export linkage, as is suggested by the previous studies discussed in section 2. Because it is difficult to determine provincial exports, the emphasis is on the importance of including an instrumented lag of the dependent variable, to be able to produce a correctly specified model with unbiased estimates of the variables included. Does FDI have a significant effect on exports? Most probably not. As a consequence, it may be concluded that the claims of the reference studies concerning the presence of a FDI-export linkage are not valid.

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Appendix

Table A.1
Derivation of the Chinese trade-weighted effective real exchange rate (index) from top 10 export source countries

STEP 1	Nominal Exchange Rate										
	USD	HKD	JPY	KRW	DEM	NLG	GBP	SGD	TWD	FRF	EUR
1993	5.80125	0.75090	0.05334	0.00718	3.41036	3.04111	8.62288	3.64107	0.21687	0.98766	
1994	8.57533	1.10961	0.08408	0.01067	5.29838	4.72457	13.13642	5.62200	0.32426	1.54932	
1995	8.35051	1.07955	0.08937	0.01083	5.83670	5.20983	13.18579	5.89537	0.31557	1.67546	
1996	8.31416	1.07502	0.07651	0.01034	5.52869	4.93434	12.98943	5.89961	0.30287	1.62593	
1997	8.28978	1.07075	0.06863	0.00891	4.79057	4.25681	13.58873	5.59713	0.28984	1.42308	
1998	8.27894	1.06884	0.06359	0.00598	4.71352	4.18153	13.72344	4.95943	0.24784	1.40587	9.69874
1999	8.27609	1.06670	0.07304	0.00696	4.51408	4.00632	13.38911	4.88579	0.25689	1.34593	8.82877
2000	8.27921	1.06257	0.07684	0.00733	3.91529	3.47488	12.55987	4.80445	0.26589	1.16740	7.65764
2001	8.28041	1.06170	0.06821	0.00643	3.79586	3.36889	11.93469	4.62420	0.24664	1.13179	7.42405
2002	8.28691	1.06271	0.06632	0.00668	7.83858	7.83858	12.46157	4.63129	0.24004	7.83858	7.83858
2003	8.28715	1.06448	0.07160	0.00698	9.38170	9.38170	13.55396	4.75772	0.24060	9.38170	9.38170
2004	8.28723	1.06416	0.07669	0.00727	10.30811	10.30811	15.18856	4.90481	0.24825	10.30811	10.30811
2005	8.20329	1.05485	0.07470	0.00804	10.21971	10.21971	14.94000	4.93188	0.25578	10.21971	10.21971
2006	7.98189	1.02758	0.06866	0.00849	10.02488	10.02488	14.70600	5.02483	0.24550	10.02488	10.02488

Source: www.oanda.com

STEP 2	Inflation, Consumer Price Index (2000=100)										
	US	HK	JP	KR	GR	NL	UK	ES	TW	FR	CN
1993	83,904	78,805	97,612	74,156	90,735	86,944	88,185	91,190	86,382	90,680	62,940
1994	86,081	85,735	98,286	78,803	93,200	89,291	90,011	94,013	89,923	92,186	78,109
1995	88,496	93,489	98,164	82,334	94,812	91,077	92,374	95,634	93,225	93,825	91,465
1996	91,095	99,410	98,294	86,388	95,940	92,378	94,629	96,953	96,090	95,781	99,057
1997	93,225	105,177	100,032	90,223	97,410	94,095	96,348	98,915	96,958	97,010	101,830
1998	94,667	108,157	100,699	97,002	97,997	95,766	97,852	98,647	98,589	97,656	101,016
1999	96,743	103,888	100,366	97,791	98,620	97,713	99,141	98,670	98,763	98,205	99,602
2000	100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000
2001	102,817	98,393	99,204	104,067	101,904	105,112	101,182	101,014	99,995	101,781	100,725
2002	104,457	95,406	98,310	106,941	103,284	109,177	102,470	100,620	99,793	103,753	99,953
2003	106,838	92,945	98,067	110,700	104,349	111,618	103,867	101,109	99,517	106,004	101,119
2004	109,703	92,588	98,051	114,675	106,217	113,158	105,263	102,799	101,121	108,486	105,063
2005	113,396	93,434	97,490	117,833	108,256	114,857	107,411	103,285	103,453	110,547	106,971
2006	117,069	95,320	97,717	120,475	110,187	116,811	109,909	104,290	104,075	112,661	108,549

Source: IMF

STEP 3.1	Real Exchange Rate (= E*Pf/Pd)										
	US	HK	JP	KR	GR	NL	UK	ES	TW	FR	
1993	7.733525	0.940176	0.082724	0.008459	4.916413	4.200926	12.08149	5.275328	0.297643	1.422959	
1994	9.45055	1.217944	0.105799	0.010765	6.32205	5.400934	15.13811	6.766712	0.373304	1.828542	
1995	8.079448	1.103439	0.095916	0.009749	6.050284	5.18773	13.31683	6.164083	0.321642	1.718691	
1996	7.645885	1.078851	0.075921	0.009018	5.35472	4.601638	12.40878	5.774301	0.293798	1.572157	
1997	7.589264	1.105944	0.067418	0.007894	4.582632	3.933463	12.85718	5.436906	0.275973	1.35572	
1998	7.758597	1.144398	0.06339	0.005742	4.57265	3.964208	13.2936	4.843123	0.241885	1.359108	
1999	8.038531	1.112601	0.0736	0.006833	4.469575	3.930338	13.32714	4.840072	0.254726	1.327052	
2000	8.27921	1.06257	0.07684	0.00733	3.91529	3.47488	12.55987	4.80445	0.26589	1.1674	
2001	8.452389	1.037119	0.06718	0.006643	3.840291	3.515619	11.98884	4.637468	0.244852	1.143656	
2002	8.660328	1.014366	0.06523	0.007147	8.099806	8.561951	12.77538	4.662195	0.239656	8.136586	
2003	8.755847	0.978432	0.069439	0.007641	9.681376	10.35578	13.9223	4.757249	0.236788	9.834924	
2004	8.653227	0.937803	0.071572	0.007935	10.42133	11.10234	15.21747	4.799116	0.238936	10.64395	
2005	8.696004	0.921361	0.068079	0.008856	10.34248	10.97312	15.00145	4.761938	0.247368	10.56135	
2006	8.608388	0.902348	0.061808	0.009423	10.17616	10.7879	14.89025	4.827677	0.235381	10.40464	

Author's calculations

Table A.1 (continued)

STEP 3.2		Real Exchange Rate Index (2000=100)										
	US	HK	JP	KR	GR	NL	UK	ES	TW	FR		
1993	93.40898	88.48132	107.657	115.4091	125.5696	120.8941	96.19116	109.8009	111.9422	121.8913		
1994	114.148	114.6225	137.6879	146.8595	161.4708	155.4279	120.5276	140.8426	140.3981	156.6337		
1995	97.58719	103.8462	124.825	132.9991	154.5296	149.2923	106.0268	128.2994	120.9682	147.2238		
1996	92.35041	101.5322	98.80358	123.0226	136.7643	132.4258	98.79706	120.1865	110.4962	134.6717		
1997	91.66652	104.082	87.73843	107.6999	117.0445	113.1971	102.3672	113.164	103.7921	116.1316		
1998	93.7118	107.701	82.49668	78.34075	116.7896	114.0819	105.8418	100.8049	90.97199	116.4218		
1999	97.09297	104.7085	95.78378	93.22579	114.1569	113.1072	106.1089	100.7414	95.8013	113.6759		
2000	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		
2001	102.0917	97.6048	87.42841	90.63225	98.08446	101.1724	95.45353	96.52443	92.08789	97.96605		
2002	104.6033	95.46344	84.89049	97.50365	206.8763	246.3956	101.7158	97.0391	90.13342	696.9836		
2003	105.757	92.08168	90.36823	104.2477	247.271	298.0185	110.8475	99.01757	89.05496	842.464		
2004	104.5175	88.25804	93.14373	108.2554	266.1701	319.5028	121.1595	99.88899	89.86257	911.7657		
2005	105.0342	86.71057	88.59868	120.8239	264.156	315.784	119.4395	99.11515	93.03398	904.69		
2006	103.976	84.92123	80.4379	128.5508	259.9081	310.454	118.5542	100.4834	88.52585	891.2659		
Author's calculations												
STEP 4		Exports to Country (USD 10 000)										
	US	HK	JP	KR	GR	NL	UK	ES	TW	FR	Total	All countries
1994	2146103	3236096	2157862	440245	476116	226707	241393	255806	224219	142433	9546980	12100632
1995	2471133	3598380	2846269	668922	567169	323208	279162	350064	309811	184184	11598302	14876974
1996	2668310	3290626	3088622	749986	584269	353686	320091	374879	280176	190679	11901324	15104753
1997	3269480	4378076	3181982	911627	649046	440463	381338	431905	339648	232878	14216443	18269664
1998	3797587	3875321	2969199	626898	735392	516151	463219	393004	386956	282276	14046003	18375711
1999	4194691	3686275	3241060	780762	777964	541295	488004	450223	394986	292111	14847371	19493087
2000	5209922	4451829	4165431	1129236	927779	668722	631010	576104	503900	370516	18634449	24920255
2001	5428269	4654664	4495757	1252069	975406	728195	678047	579188	500024	368565	19660184	26615464
2002	6994579	5846315	4843384	1553456	1137185	910756	805943	698422	658572	407186	23855798	32559597
2003	9246677	7627437	5940870	2009477	1744211	1350124	1082372	886377	900409	729353	31517307	43822777
2004	12494203	10086857	7350904	2781156	2375573	1851882	1496696	1268760	1354443	992139	42052612.5	59332558
2005	16289075	12447325	8398628	3510778	3252713	2587574	1897647	1663226	1654956	1163936	52865858	76195341
Total	74210029	67179201	52679968	16414612	14202823	10498763	8764922	7927958	7508100	5356256	264742632	
Author's calculations												
STEP 5		Trade Share/Weight										
	US	HK	JP	KR	GR	NL	UK	ES	TW	FR	Sum	% All countries
1994	0.224794	0.338965	0.226026	0.046114	0.049871	0.023746	0.025285	0.026794	0.023486	0.014919	1	0.788965
1995	0.21306	0.310251	0.245404	0.057674	0.048901	0.027867	0.024069	0.030182	0.026712	0.01588	1	0.779614
1996	0.224203	0.276492	0.259519	0.063017	0.049093	0.029718	0.026895	0.031499	0.023542	0.016022	1	0.787919
1997	0.229979	0.307959	0.223824	0.064125	0.045655	0.030983	0.026824	0.030381	0.023891	0.016381	1	0.778145
1998	0.270368	0.275902	0.211391	0.044632	0.052356	0.036747	0.032979	0.02798	0.027549	0.020097	1	0.764379
1999	0.282521	0.248278	0.218292	0.052586	0.052397	0.036457	0.032868	0.030323	0.026603	0.019674	1	0.761674
2000	0.279586	0.238903	0.223534	0.060599	0.049788	0.035886	0.033863	0.030916	0.027041	0.019883	1	0.747763
2001	0.276105	0.236756	0.228673	0.063686	0.049613	0.037039	0.034488	0.02946	0.025433	0.018747	1	0.738675
2002	0.293202	0.245069	0.203028	0.065119	0.047669	0.038178	0.033784	0.029277	0.027606	0.017069	1	0.732681
2003	0.293384	0.242008	0.188495	0.063758	0.055341	0.042838	0.034342	0.028124	0.028569	0.023141	1	0.719199
2004	0.297109	0.239863	0.174803	0.066135	0.056491	0.044037	0.035591	0.030171	0.032208	0.023593	1	0.708761
2005	0.308122	0.235451	0.158867	0.066409	0.061528	0.048946	0.035896	0.031461	0.031305	0.022017	1	0.69382
Author's calculations												
STEP 6.1	Trade-weighted Effective Real Exchange Rate					STEP 6.2	Effective Real Exchange Rate Index (2000=1000)					
	1994	3.605337					1994	126.605117				
	1995	3.070737					1995	115.023989				
	1996	2.980153					1996	104.023505				
	1997	2.971493					1997	99.0951933				
	1998	3.420044					1998	97.4508379				
	1999	3.558886					1999	100.671408				
	2000	3.510102					2000	100				
	2001	3.49358					2001	95.9889235				
	2002	4.228106					2002	117.580048				
	2003	4.644858					2003	132.074636				
	2004	4.831768					2004	136.501613				
	2005	5.009771					2005	136.824228				
Author's calculations												

Table A.2
Comparison FE and FD

Explanatory variables	FE estimation		FD estimation	
	Parameter estimates	t value	Parameter estimates	t value
FDI	0.037	0.79	0.037	-0.58
Other Investment	0.003	0.41	0.003	0.43
GDP	-0.009	-1.30	0.007	0.18
Exchange rate	0.393 ***	11.63	0.238 ***	5.66
TIME	0.058 ***	5.82	0.011 ***	5.65
Constant	-105.698 ***	-5.28	-	-
F value	71.98		46.41	
R2	0.776		0.450	
N	266		234	

Notes: Both estimations have clustered standard errors. All variables are lagged log variables with exception of the time trend. Superscripts ***, **, * indicate significance levels of 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively. The estimation results from the within regression and first differencing procedure are rather similar for FDI, Other Investment, and GDP. But, the sign of the parameters for FDI and GDP are different. The Exchange rate parameter is almost twice as large for the FE estimation as for the FD estimation. As both regressions have the same variables, the F value and R² can be compared. Even by taking into account the number of observations, the R² of the FE estimation is much larger. The same is true for the F value.

Figure A.1
Provincial map of China

Table A.3
Cumulative FDI- and export inflows by sub sample and province, 1995-2003

Sub sample	Province	FDI (USD 10.000)	Sub sample	Province	Exports (USD 10.000)
Coastal	Guangdong	11044738	Coastal	Guangdong	80243521
Coastal	Jiangsu	6263894	Coastal	Jiangsu	22163563
Coastal	Shanghai	3475581	Coastal	Shanghai	20928382
Coastal	Fujian	3434904	Coastal	Zhejiang	16297964
Coastal	Shandong	3065931	Coastal	Shandong	13155729
Coastal	Liaoning	1979311	Coastal	Fujian	11220085
Coastal	Zhejiang	1873568	Coastal	Beijing	10166325
Coastal	Tianjin	1647878	Coastal	Liaoning	9108634
Coastal	Beijing	1573676	Coastal	Tianjin	6988787
Inland	Hubei	1008250	Coastal	Hebei	3360575
Coastal	Hebei	819785	Inland	Anhui	1738401
Inland	Hunan	704896	Inland	Hubei	1655180
Coastal	Hainan	558925	Inland	Sichuan	1650880
Coastal	Guangxi	549044	Coastal	Guangxi	1450281
Inland	Jiangxi	517391	Inland	Henan	1449101
Inland	Henan	479702	Inland	Hunan	1418138
Inland	Heilongjiang	398220	Inland	Heilongjiang	1334553
Inland	Sichuan	393140	Inland	Shanxi	1157425
Inland	Anhui	336778	Inland	Shaanxi	1143975
Inland	Shaanxi	315250	Inland	Jilin	1143749
Inland	Jilin	308215	Inland	Yunnan	1112646
Inland	Chongqing	205351	Inland	Jiangxi	972446
Inland	Shanxi	199054	Inland	Xinjiang	913069
Inland	Yunnan	101647	Coastal	Hainan	717932
Inland	Inner Mongolia	83656	Inland	Chongqing	653432
Inland	Gansu	49643	Inland	Inner Mongolia	629580
Inland	Guizhou	36115	Inland	Gansu	397221
Inland	Xinjiang	26302	Inland	Guizhou	385964
Inland	Ningxia	15970	Inland	Ningxia	248669
Inland	Qinghai	11867	Inland	Qinghai	123698
Inland	Tibet	N/A	Inland	Tibet	59878

Source: China Statistical Yearbook 1996-2004 (CSY, 1996-2004)

Table A.4
Exclusion of lagged exports

Full sample					
Explanatory variables	OLS estimation		OLS estimation		
	Parameter estimates	t value	Parameter estimates	t value	
Exports	1.011 ***	70.19	-	-	
FDI	-0.001	-0.10	0.724 ***	10.46	
Other Investment	0.002	0.50	-0.010	-0.47	
GDP	0.004	0.82	-0.056 **	-2.46	
Exchange rate	0.130 ***	3.45	0.381 ***	4.68	
TIME	0.015 *	1.91	0.034	1.52	
Constant	-29.869 *	-1.97	-62.443	-1.42	
F value	4841.87		56.18		
R ²	0.988		0.795		
N	266		266		

Notes: Pooled least squares regression model with clustered standard errors. All are lagged log variables except the trend variable. Superscripts ***, **, * indicate significance levels of 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively. When the lagged exports variable is included in the model, the effect of FDI on exports seems to be very small and insignificant. When compared to the parameter in the second model, where the lag of exports is excluded, the effect of FDI on exports becomes very large and significant. Also, the effect of the exchange rate on exports increases. This suggests that the lagged exports variable in the error term is highly correlated with FDI and the exchange rate. As a result, all explanatory variables are biased. This could also be very well true for the results of Zhang and Song (2000) and Sun (2001).

Table A.5
Exclusion of exports under the assumption $E(c_i x_i) \neq 0$

Full sample				
Explanatory variables	GMM estimation		FE estimation	
	Parameter estimates	z value	Parameter estimates	t value
Exports	0.41 *	1.66	-	-
FDI	-0.043	-1.06	0.037	0.79
Other Investment	0.006	1.64	0.003	0.41
GDP	0.012 **	2.40	-0.009	-1.30
Exchange rate	0.214 ***	5.97	0.393 ***	11.63
TIME	0.065 ***	3.65	0.058 ***	5.82
Constant	-	-	-105.698 ***	-5.28
F value	8.34		71.98	
R ²	-		0.776	
N	233		266	

Notes: GMM and FE estimation have clustered standard errors. All variables are lagged log variables with exception of the time trend. Superscripts ***, **, * indicate significance levels of 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively. The within estimation for the parameter of the FDI variable illustrates the fact that, ceteris paribus, FDI has no significant effect on exports.